

Participant Information Sheet

The SAFER Wearables Study

A study of the acceptability and performance of wearables for atrial fibrillation screening in older adults.

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Invitation to take part

Thank you for your contribution so far to the SAFER research programme. The programme is looking at how to identify atrial fibrillation (AF), an irregular heartbeat which can increase one's risk of stroke if not treated. The recordings you took using a handheld device (shown below on the left) have been very valuable. They will help us determine whether screening for AF reduces the incidence of strokes. Thank you.

The first study

This follow-on study

We are now inviting you to take part in a follow-on study about using wearables (like watches) to screen for AF.

It's entirely up to you whether you take part. Before deciding, it's important to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve. Please read the following information carefully. Discuss it with others if you wish. If you are interested in taking part then telephone us on 01223 331 063 to discuss the study further. Do ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

Study Summary

Why?

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is an irregular heartbeat, which increases the risk of stroke unless it is treated. We (researchers at the University of Cambridge) want to find out if new wearable devices could be used to screen for AF. We want to see if wearable devices are acceptable to patients, and if they accurately identify AF.

Who?

We are inviting selected people who took part in the SAFER Study to also take part in this study. We are inviting some people who did have AF in the previous study, and some people who did not. Note: you will have already been informed if you did have AF.

What?

We are asking participants to wear three devices at the same time for seven days. The devices are:

Chest-patch

Wristband

Watch

We will also ask participants to complete a questionnaire on how they found wearing the devices.

We will find out how participants found wearing each device, and how accurately each device identifies AF.

Where?

Participants take part at home.

How?

We will send the devices to participants. We will be in touch by telephone to explain how to use the devices. Participants will wear the devices for a week. They will return them via post (we will pay for postage).

In this research study we will use information from you. We will only use information that we need for the research study. We will let very few people know your name or contact details, and only if they really need it for this study. Everyone involved in this study will keep your data safe and secure. We will also follow all privacy rules. At the end of the study we will save some of the data in case we need to check it and for future research. We will make sure no-one can work out who you are from the reports we write. This information sheet tells you more about this.

What next?

✓ **I AM INTERESTED in taking part**

If you are interested in taking part: please read on for further details. Then telephone the study team to discuss the study further and answer any questions: **01223 331 063**.

X **I DO NOT want to take part**

If you are not interested: it would be helpful to understand why. If you are willing, please complete and return the enclosed reply slip in the enclosed Freepost envelope.

Read on for further details

Further Details of the Study

Why are we doing this study?

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is a heart condition that causes an irregular heartbeat. It affects up to 1 in 10 people over the age of 65. It is often not noticed as it may not cause symptoms and can occur only intermittently. It is important to identify AF as it increases the risk of having a stroke 5-fold if it isn't treated.

New wearable devices, such as smart watches and wristbands, could help identify AF. They can monitor the heart throughout the day, allowing us to identify AF even if it only occurs once in a while. Previous research has shown they can be useful in younger adults and hospital patients. We want to see how older adults find wearing them, and whether the devices accurately identify AF in the general population.

The results will help us make recommendations about which devices may be suitable for further development and clinical use.

Why have I been invited?

You have been invited because you were previously screened for AF in the SAFER Programme. We are recruiting 130 people to take part in this follow-up study: half of these have AF, and half don't. Note: you will have already been informed if you have AF. We only need 130 people because this initial investigation will help us understand how well devices currently perform, and how to improve them for potential use in screening.

I have a heart condition. Can I take part?

Yes, half of the people taking part have AF. It's important for us to find out how well the devices work for people with and without AF. However, if you have a pacemaker or other implantable device then you cannot take part.

Do I have to take part?

No, it is entirely voluntary and your usual medical care will not be influenced by whether or not you take part.

What will I have to do?

1. *Consent:* We will ask you to confirm your consent to take part by posting the enclosed consent form to us in the prepaid envelope. If you would like a copy of the consent form then please ask us.
2. *Device delivery:* We will send you the devices, a detailed instruction leaflet, and a questionnaire.
3. *Training:* We will explain how to wear and use the devices over the telephone, referring to the instruction leaflet.
4. *Wear the devices:* We will ask you to wear the devices for seven days, going about your daily life as normal. The devices are waterproof. If you have chest hair then you will need to shave a small area for the chest-patch to stick to. We will ask you to use the watch four times each day to record your heart beating for 30 seconds. We will ask you to plug in a mobile phone which will collect information from the devices (this is optional, and if you are happy to use a mobile phone then we will provide one). We will telephone you during the study to check for any problems.
5. *Questionnaire:* We will ask you to complete a questionnaire on the devices after wearing them.
6. *Return devices:* At the end we will telephone you and help arrange for the devices and questionnaire to be sent back to us (which we will pay for).

We will give you an instruction leaflet with further details of each step.

Are there any benefits to taking part?

There are not any direct benefits to you of taking part. We will not be able to give you any information on your health from this study. However, you may find it rewarding to know that you are playing a vital role in research that aims to prevent strokes in the future.

Are there any risks involved in taking part?

Some people may experience skin irritation when wearing the devices. To try to avoid this, we have selected devices which are unlikely to cause

irritation. If a device does cause you irritation then you should remove it straight away. We will always be happy to help over the phone (our contact details are at the end of this information sheet).

All our data collection, storage and handling processes will comply with the relevant security policies and regulations. We will do our best to ensure the security and confidentiality of your data.

Your usual medical care will not be affected.

When would I take part?

We can be flexible to fit in with your schedule – give us a call and we can discuss mutually convenient dates.

How will I know if the devices are working?

Each device tells the user if it is working – further details of how to check are given in an instruction leaflet which comes with the devices.

Will anyone be in contact?

Please contact the study team (on **01223 331 063**) if you are interested in taking part. The study team call you during the study to help you use the devices and check for any problems. You can also contact us if you need to.

What if the devices get damaged?

The devices are waterproof and robust so should not get damaged, although this may happen once in a while. If a device gets damaged then don't worry, just let us know (using the contact details at the end). We will be grateful for your participation regardless.

Will I need to write down the readings?

No, you will not need to write down any readings. The measurements are automatically recorded in the devices. If you are happy to use a mobile phone, then it will collect more readings from the wrist-worn devices than could otherwise be collected. We will get the measurements from the devices and phone when you send them back.

What if I don't want to carry on with the study?

You may have a break from wearing the devices or stop wearing them at any time. Any feedback you give in the questionnaire on why you stopped wearing them will help us understand how to improve the devices and make them even more comfortable.

If you change your mind about taking part you can withdraw your consent at any time. If this is the case, please contact us using the details at the end of this information sheet. Any information collected from you up till then will be used for the purposes described in this information sheet. We will still expect you to return the devices to us.

Who is organising and funding the study?

The trial is being organised by the University of Cambridge (the study sponsor). The University of Cambridge is responsible for the conduct of the study. It is funded by the British Heart Foundation.

Who has reviewed / approved the study?

To protect your interests, all research in the NHS is looked at by an independent group of people, called a Research Ethics Committee. This study has been reviewed and given favourable opinion by the East Midlands - Leicester Central NHS Research Ethics Committee. The science and size of the study has been reviewed by independent experts.

How have patients and the public been involved in the study?

Patient representatives and members of the public have been involved with: choosing the research topic, designing the study, and designing the documents (including this information sheet).

What if something goes wrong?

If you have any concern about any aspect of this study, you should speak to us (the research team) and we will do our best to answer your questions and resolve any issues – our contact details are at the end of this information sheet.

If you remain unhappy and wish to complain formally, please contact the Business & Operations Manager in the Department of Public Health and Primary Care at the University of Cambridge:

Phone: 01223 748623

Email: PHPC_BOM@medschl.cam.ac.uk

Post: Business & Operations Manager | Department of Public Health & Primary Care | Strangeways Research Laboratory | Worts Causeway | Cambridge | CB1 8RN

In the event that something does go wrong and you are harmed during the research and this is due to someone's negligence then you may have grounds for legal action for compensation against the University of Cambridge or an individual through their professional indemnity (if appropriate) but you may have to pay your legal costs. The normal National Health Service complaints mechanisms will still be available to you (if appropriate). The University of Cambridge has arranged insurance in case something goes wrong and you are harmed but it is not due to anybody's fault (no-fault compensation).

How will I find out the results of the study?

At the end of the study the results will be made available on our study website – please see the contact details at the end of this information sheet for the link. If you would like us to send you a copy of the results please get in touch with us.

Data Confidentiality

How will we use information about you?

We will need to use information from you for this research project. This information will include:

- “Personal data”: your name, address, contact details, and date of birth.
- “Study data”: details of your health; your feedback on the study and the devices; and data recorded by the devices (measurements of your heart and physical activity, and technical device information).

People will use this information to do the research or to check your records to make sure that the research is being done properly. People who do not need to know who you are will not be able to see your personal data. Your data will have a code number instead.

We will inform your GP that you are taking part in the study. We will share your name, address and telephone number with a courier in order to send the devices to you.

We will keep all information about you safe and secure. Some of your study data will be sent to the wearable device manufacturers where necessary (including PulseOn, in Finland). No personal data will be shared with device manufacturers.

Once we have finished the study, we will keep some of the data so we can check the results. We will write our reports in a way that no-one can work out that you took part in the study.

What are your choices about how your information is used?

You can stop being part of the study at any time, without giving a reason, but we will keep information about you that we already have.

We need to manage your records in specific ways for the research to be reliable. This means that we won't be able to let you see or change the data we hold about you.

What will happen to the information after the study?

The information collected will be used firstly for this specific study. It could also be useful for further research, potentially helping to make further developments to improve people's health. To allow others to use it, we will share your anonymous study data with others, and make it publicly available, after you finish participating. We will ensure that anything that could be used to identify you has been removed.

The SAFER Wearables Study is part of an important long-term programme of research that relies on long-term follow-up of participants. The SAFER Programme research team will retain your personal and study data indefinitely to meet the purposes of medical research and any legal, accounting or reporting requirements.

Where can you find out more about how your information is used?

You can find out more about how we use your information:

- at: www.hra.nhs.uk/information-about-patients/
- at: www.hra.nhs.uk/patientdataandresearch
- by asking one of the research team using the contact details at the end of this information sheet
- by sending an email to the University of Cambridge's Data Protection team (data.protection@admin.cam.ac.uk) or its Data Protection Officer (dpo@admin.cam.ac.uk).

Contact Us

Who do I contact if I have any questions?

If you or someone on your behalf needs to contact the research team you can do so as follows:

Phone: contact us using the following number during working hours (Monday to Friday 9am – 5pm): **01223 331 063**. If we miss your call or if you call outside these hours, there is an answer phone on this number. If you leave a message we will respond to you at the earliest opportunity.

Email: safer-wearables@medschl.cam.ac.uk

Address:

The SAFER Wearables Study
University of Cambridge
Primary Care Unit
Strangeways Research Laboratory
2 Worts Causeway
Cambridge
CB1 8RN

Website: www.safer-wearables.phpc.cam.ac.uk

The study is registered with *ClinicalTrials.gov*:
<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT04715555>